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23_Arabic

1. Phonetic and Phonology

1.1. Segmental and phonotactic patterns

- semi-vowels /w, j / may be syllable initial and final
 - corresponding vowels /u, i / may not be syllable initial
 - words containing two or three long vowels are common
 - geminates:
 - o tendency to be realized shorter in final position as in medial position
 - o same distribution like consonant clusters consisting of different consonants, that means they occur only medially and finally
 - o syllabification like consonant clusters consisting of different consonants, that means the first consonant belongs to another syllable than the second
 - o can contain a morpheme boundary; ex.: as-saqf ‘ART-ceiling’ (Kästner)
 - word-finally /b/ can be released or not released
 - o voiceless when in contact with a voiceless consonant
 - o possible to be reduced or dropped when word-finally
 - /t/, /d/:
 - o generally unreleased in word-finally position
 - o voicedness can be reduced or dropped in word-final position
- velarised counterparts: same processes
- /ʔ/ generally unreleased word-finally
 - o total assimilation on preceding vowel results in a long vowel; ex.:
taʔri:x > ta:ri:x ‘history, date’ (Kästner)
 - /ɖ/ voiceless in syllable final position following voiceless consonants or in word final position
 - o voiced generally when word and syllable initial
 - /z/ may be slightly devoiced in word final position
 - /w/, /j/ treated like other consonants – syllable initial and final element
 - long vowels:
 - o reduction of length in word final position
 - o can contain morpheme boundary
 - o as diphthongs distribution limited to one syllable
 - o can be decomposed in its single units if the consonantal unit becomes the onset of the following syllable when adding a vowel;
ex.: majda:n > maja:di:n ‘court’ (Kästner)
 - o occurrence in one syllable limited to preconsonantal position and word final position

- restrictions word finally and initially depends on whether the word is in context or pausal position
 - the single word based on its syllable structure is embedded in the context so that a phonetic marking of word boundaries seems to be impossible except from accent
 - different from context forms, pausal forms can be only bound simply i.e. initially or finally
 - special feature of pre-pausal position: minimal one element of the last syllable, maximal the whole last syllable is not realized
 - names, titles, loanwords are always realized as they would be in pre-pausal position
 - context position:
 - o word final syllable CV attracts the initial C of the following word
 - o final V: is shortened; ex.: fi: l-bajt > fi-l-bajt 'in the house' (Kästner)
 - o word final consonant: syllabic conditioned short vowel added ;
ex.: man r-rasu:l > manirrasu:l 'who is the messenger?' (Kästner)
- formation of syllables whose elements belong to different words

1.2. Phonological processes

- emphasised consonants:
 - o phonetic effect on contiguous segments to the left and right
 - o non-emphatic consonants become emphasised, vowel are lowered and backed
 - o also a backing effect have non-emphatic consonants /r/, /x/, /ʃ/, /q/
 - o proposal of some linguists: that emphasis is not a property of the four individual consonants which are conventionally treated as such but rather a prosodic or suprasegmental feature whose minimal domain is a consonant and an adjacent vowel
- long vowels shortened in pre-pausal position;
ex.: adduwalu l-kubra: > adduwalu lkubra 'superpower' (Holes)
 - o main exceptions are small number of pronominal affixes which are generally kept long in pause
- selective application of phonological rules depending on whether they are nouns or verbs – maintain important morphological distinctions
- shortening of vowel in CV:C in declination with a/u inserted in C-skeleton
- stems C2=C3:
 - o C2VC3 is stable if it forms a closed syllable; ex.: malaltu 'I got bored' (Holes)
 - o V separating C2, C3 is deleted in an open syllable;
ex.: malla, not: malal-a 'he became bored' (Holes)
 - o Same underlying string is treated differently in some types of nouns, noun plurals, verbal nouns, other nouns of form C1VC2VC3 remain where two syllables C2VC3 occur as a result of the suffixing of case endings;
ex.: malal-an 'boredom (acc)'
 - o It seems from this that the short vowel deletion rule operates or does not just in order to maintain an important surface morphological distinction in form which are underlying similar
- Assimilation of vowels on uvular, pharyngeal, velarised consonants
 - o All vowels in direct contact but also more distant vowels concerned

- Scopus of assimilation of different size, dependent on consonant, speed of speech etc., but minimal one syllable, maximal three syllables
- Total assimilation of the prefixed article on some consonants in word final position; ex.: al-naum > an-naum ‘the sleep’
- Assimilation of voicelessness when voiced consonants get in contact with voiceless consonants in a word; ex.: **ʕ**ab•s ‘prison’
- Assimilation between vowel: assimilation of /u/ of the suffixed personal pronoun on the word final /i/ (case suffix) of the noun; ex.: fi: kitab-i-hi (genitive) [nominative: kitab-u-hu]
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1.3. Syllable structure

- all syllables begin with a single consonant and are either open CV or CVV or closed CVC, CVVC, CVCC, CVVCC
 - positional restriction:
 - spoken prose of reading style allow only CV, CVV, CVC
 - CVVC would occur as it does in certain common types of junctured phrase, it becomes CVC; ex.: fi: + l-ma:dli: ‘in the past’ would be fi:l.ma:.dli: , vowel shortening fi + l-madli: (Holes)
- few cases where CVVC or CVCC are admitted in non-final position so as to maintain a grammatical distinction; ex.: mu.maT.Ti.lu: + S.Sa.ri.ka ‘the company representatives’
mu.maT.Ti.lu + S.Sa.ri.ka ‘ the company representative’
(Holes)
article of the second member of noun-noun-group gets part of syllabification of the first – it seems that syllabification of both converges – syllabification as one word, no pause in between
- syllable boundaries in connected speech are not necessarily coterminous with word boundaries
- superheavy syllables only in prepause position
- no more than one SHS per word
- if V2 in V1C(=y/w)V2(:) occurs in open syllable:
 - low V1 assimilates any V2
 - low V2 is stable
 - high front V assimilates high back V in all positions
 - low V1 reduces any high V2
 - low V2 is stable
 - high V2 assimilates V1

1.4. Stress

- SHS get stress
- words without SHS: stress assignment depends on the number of syllables in the word

- in words containing three or less syllables – accent is on the penultimate; ex.: málik ‘king’
 - o exceptions sometimes: antepenultimate CVV is stressed if penultimate is CV; if antepenultimate and penultimate are both CV, the antepenultimate is stressed; ex.: hárika ‘movement’ (Holes)
- in words of four or more syllables containing CVV, CVV is stressed (the CVV nearest the end of the word, if there are two); ex.: muná:saba ‘occasion’, ba:haTú:hu ‘they discussed it’ (Holes)
- if there is no CV then the antepenultimate is stressed, ex.: katábtuhu ‘I wrote it’ (Holes)

1.6. Minimal word

- independent words: CVV or CVC minimal
- there are particles CV, but they don’t seem to be phonological independent

1.7. Clitic and particles

- pronominal clitics: it is one set of two sets for pronominal forms: suffixed to verbs, nouns, prepositions, particle
- definite article :
 - o not on finite verbs
 - o not written separately
 - o deletion of ‘a’ in al- in connected speech
- connectives, certain prepositions seem to be clitics (attachable to different word categories and phonological bound)

1.8. Other Questions

- in prepause position inflectional suffixes which mark indefiniteness are not treated alike: /in/ ‘gen.’, /an/ ‘acc.’ may be retained, /un/ ‘nom.’ always omitted
- pausal and junctural phenomena:
 - o final short vowels which appear in pre-juncture position are omitted in pre-pause; ex.: s-sala:mi in pre-juncture position, s-sala:m in pre-pause position ‘the peace’ (Holes)
 - o it seems that there is a distinction to be drawn between treatment of –in as marker of a noun in the genitive case and –in as a marker of an attributive adjective which is in agreement with a genitive head noun when in phrasal-final pre-pause position :
 - adjective realised without –in when in pre-pause position but nouns which are in a genitive relationship with another noun or which are governed by a preposition retain –in in pre-pause position
 - o retaining pre-pausal –in do not occur at the end of a sentence but at the boundary of clauses or phrases within a sentence
 - o pre-pausal behaviour of –an also seems to depend on its functional and grammatical status – in some cases by some speakers retained in others not
 - o the decision to use phrasal or non-phrasal forms may depend on the type of grammatical and textual boundary with which the pause coincides, depends on

what counts as phrase

- [my objection: these observations are from spoken MSA – but there are no native speakers, so it might be dialectal influence]
- t-morphem which marks feminine gender in certain nouns and adjectives disappears in pre-pause position together with –u/-a/-i (definite) and the –un/-in/-an (indefinite) case inflections suffixed to it, but prejuncturally retained; ex.: al-hurri:yati hurri:ya in pre-pause ‘the freedom’ (Holes)

2. Morphology

- morphology of root and pattern:
 - restrictions on combination of consonants which can occupy the three positions in the root:
 - sonorants /l, n, r, w, y/ may occur in any position with any other consonant preceding or following
 - C1 and C2 may not be homorganic
 - Few roots where C1 and C3 are either identical or homorganic
 - Pattern: morphologically – templates augment the root by lengthening middle radical, inserting a vowel between radical, adding consonantal prefixes, and a combination of these
- Infix -t- : after C1 > C1tC2C3
- Discontinuous bound affixes : indicating mood, person, number, gender affixes - on verbs (prefixed and suffixed part on stem except in past); ex.: ja-ktub-u ‘he writes’
- Impermissible strings arising through morphological processes trigger morphophonological adjustments:
 - If /w/ or /y/ occurs singly and especially intervocalically and if they are weak (as opposite of strong = behave like consonants) processes:
 - Dropping: ex.: WSĪL ya-sīlil-u not: yawśīlilu ‘he arrives’
 - Assimilation to infix -t- : ex.: ttasġal not : wtasġal ‘he arrived’
- Noun – noun- combinations: status constructus – constructions
- Canonical type of the verb phrase :
 - (AUX)(Particle)(NEG)verb(pronoun enclitic)
 - verb is the only one which is obligatory
 - modal, aspectual particles ‘qad, laqad’; prefix ‘sa-‘ postposed
 - bound pronominal object enclitic morphemes
 - negative particles ‘lam, lan, la:, ma:’ are “orthographically separate words” (Holes), precedes verb, noun etc.
- some aspectual distinctions are lexicalized, idiomaticised – consist of verb + verb – strings, in which both verbs are inflected in the normal way
 - first verb has a literal meaning from which its aspectual force is derived
- preposition:
 - govern genitive case
 - ‘min’ ‘from’ becomes ‘mini’ before a word beginning with hamzat al-wasl connected with vowel [i] (hamza = glottal plosive, wasl means that the stop is not realised, end of the first entity and beginning of the second are contracted); ex.: min ‘ibni > mini bni ‘from my son’ (Holes)

- min > mina before the definite article (hamzat al-wasl vocalised with [a])
vowel of the Hamzat al-wasl of the following word is dropped
ex.: min al-bait > mina – lbait ‘from the house’ (Holes)
 - compound preposition ‘bisabab’ ‘because of, owing to’: bi-sabab ‘with-reason’ (Holes)
 - prepositional object or genitive pronouns take the form of a suffix – the same suffixes, subject to the same provisions as the possessive adjective suffixes
 - any short vowel ending a preposition is dropped before the 1st person singular suffix
 - prepositions ‘min’ ‘from’ and ‘ʿan’ ‘about’ double final ‘n’ before 1st singular suffix
 - prepositional ending –a becomes –ai before prepositional object suffix;
a: + 1st singular –i: becomes ‘aja’
 - preposition ‘li’ becomes ‘la’ before all suffixes except 1st singular
 - after any prepositions ending –i:, -ai the 3rd person suffixes –hu, -huma:, -hum, -huna become –hi, -hima:, -him, -hina
 - some prepositions and particles are orthographically prefixes, they all are of the shape CV: li ‘for’, bi ‘with’, fa connector ‘so that’, wa ‘and’, ka ‘like, as’
 - preposition ‘baina’ ‘between’ governs two concepts:
 - if either of the concept is a pronoun, baina is repeated;
ex.: baina misḷr wa-lubna:n ‘between Egypt and Lebanon’;
bainana: wa-bainakum ‘between you and us’
- periphrastic constructions:
- auxiliary ka:na (past) ‘be’
 - habitual past: Aux (past tense) + main verb (present tense);
ex.: ka:na jaf?alu ‘he did (habitually)’
 - pluperfect : AUX (past tense) + particle ‘qad’ + main verb (past tense);
ex.: ka:na qad fa?ala ‘he had done’
 - completed action in future : AUX (present tense) + particle ‘qad’ + main verb (past tense) ;
ex. : jaku:nu qad fa?ala ‘he will have done’